
Research Article

New combinations in *Dendrocalamus* (Poaceae, Bambusoideae)

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Abstract: Six new combinations are proposed here in the genus *Dendrocalamus* Nees.

Keywords: *Dendrocalamus*, *Sinocalamus*, Vietnam

Introduction

The genus *Dendrocalamus* Nees is distributed across the Indian subcontinent, southern China, and Southeast Asia, and comprises about 80 species (POWO, 2025). This includes six species originally described from Vietnam under the genus *Sinocalamus* McClure. In Myanmar, *Dendrocalamus* is represented by 30 species, including six that were also previously placed in *Sinocalamus*. Currently, *Sinocalamus* McClure is considered a synonym of *Dendrocalamus* Nees (Soreng et al., 2022). Accordingly, the six validly published species from Vietnam under *Sinocalamus* are hereby transferred to *Dendrocalamus*.

New combinations

Dendrocalamus bacthaiensis (T.Q.Nguyen), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sinocalamus bacthaiensis* T.Q.Nguyen, Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 75(2): 222. 1990.

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Dendrocalamus maiensis (T.Q.Nguyen), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sinocalamus maiensis* T.Q.Nguyen, Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 75: 224 (1990).

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Dendrocalamus nhatrangensis (T.Q.Nguyen), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sinocalamus nhatrangensis* T.Q.Nguyen & Vucan, Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 76: 993 (1991).

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Dendrocalamus rugosiglumis (T.Q.Nguyen), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sinocalamus rugosiglumis* T.Q.Nguyen, Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 74: 1662 (1989).

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Dendrocalamus sang (T.Q.Nguyen), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sinocalamus sang* T.Q.Nguyen, Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 75: 223 (1990).

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

Dendrocalamus yentuensis (T.Q.Nguyen), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Sinocalamus yentuensis* T.Q.Nguyen, Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 75: 223 (1990).

Distribution: Endemic to Vietnam.

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References

- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available from: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 10 May 2025).
- Soreng, R.J., Peterson, P.M., Zuloaga, F.O., Romaschenko, K., Clark, L.G., Teisher, J.K., Gillespie, L.J., Barberá, P., Welker, C.A.D., Kellogg, E.A., Li, D.Z. and Davidse, G. (2022). A worldwide phylogenetic classification of the Poaceae (Gramineae) III: An update. *Journal of Systematics and Evolution* 60(3): 476–521. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jse.12847>